

Fingerprint matching using the onion peeling approach and turning function

Abstract: Fingerprint, as one of the most popular and robust biometric traits, can be used in automatic identification and verification systems to identify individuals. Fingerprint matching is a vital and challenging issue in fingerprint recognition systems. Most fingerprint matching algorithms are minutiae-based. The minutiae points are the ways that the fingerprint ridges can be discontinuous. Ridge ending and ridge bifurcation are two frequently used minutiae in most fingerprint matching algorithms. This article presents a new minutiae-based fingerprint matching using the onion peeling approach. In the proposed method, fingerprints are aligned to find the matched minutiae points. Then, the nested convex polygons of matched minutiae points are constructed and the comparison between peer-to-peer polygons is performed by the turning function distance. Simplicity, accuracy, and low time complexity of the onion peeling approach are three important factors that make it a standard method for fingerprint matching purposes. The performance of the proposed algorithm is evaluated on the database FVC2002. Since the fingerprints that the difference between the number of their layers is more than 2 and the a minutiae matching score lower than 0.15 are ignored, better results are obtained.

Keywords: Fingerprint Matching, Minutiae, Convex Layers, Turning Function, Computational Geometry.

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